

SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL BASIS OF EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF TOLERANCE AND INTERNATIONAL HARMONY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14434939>

Annotation. This article is devoted to the education of youth in the spirit of interethnic harmony and tolerance, the formation of youth spirituality, focusing on the fact that more than one hundred and thirty nations and nationalities living in the country participate in good deeds in this direction, since the future and stability and development of the country are closely connected with the education of youth in the spirit of interethnic harmony and tolerance.

Keywords: Youth, education, interethnic harmony, tolerance, national separatism, chauvinistic worldview, tolerance.

In Uzbekistan, attention to youth is considered one of the main directions of state policy, raising them to be physically healthy, spiritually and mentally developed, independent-thinking, loyal to the Motherland, having strict life views and respect for the culture, traditions and religious values of other nations is defined as one of the priority tasks.

It is known that the historical development of any country, the rapid development of the country, the achievement of certain achievements, the well-being of the people are closely related to the level of attention paid to the spirituality, education and future of the youth in this country. In this sense, the issue of youth in Uzbekistan is one of the most priority areas of state policy, and President Shavkat Mirziyoyev pays special attention to "Education of a mature, potential, creative-thinking generation that connects the development of the country with its own destiny, only science and education are necessary to build the foundations of the Third Renaissance." One of the multifaceted directions of education is to form a sense of respect for representatives of other nationalities, their national and religious values in young people, to be free from chauvinism, racism, nationalism, nationalism, as well as to create a system of education in the spirit of an intolerant attitude to religious extremism and terrorism.

In this regard, legal, economic, spiritual-educational, ideological-ideological activities aimed at fully ensuring the interests of young people, positively directing their influence on society, and serving to guarantee their interests, regardless of their nationality, are being systematically implemented in our country. In the educational system, purposeful activities are being organized to educate the young generation in the spirit of respect for national and universal values, which can resist harmful influences and currents alien to our mentality.

As the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated, "... currently, youth education remains an issue that will never lose its relevance and importance for us. Today's rapidly changing world opens up new and great opportunities for humanity and young people. At the same time, they are exposed to various evil dangers that have never been seen before. The evil forces are turning simple, naive children against their parents, their country, and are taking their lives. In such a tense and dangerous situation, we as parents, teachers, the community, and the

community need to increase vigilance and awareness in this matter. We should raise our children ourselves, not leave them in the hands of others."

It should be noted that protecting young people from the influence of foreign ideas, educating them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony, as well as educating them as selfless and patriots with a high morale, a firm life position, and a broad worldview, requires the entire family, educational system, public organizations, local and other state organizations and civil institutions are equally responsible. Therefore, in our country, the role of state and local management systems and educational institutions in the stable maintenance and development of inter-ethnic relations, the strengthening and development of the mutual harmony of representatives of different nationalities, as well as the improvement of the activities of civil society institutions, and the further raising of the morale based on tolerance among young people, are given special attention as a priority task. specifies that they give.

Because inter-ethnic harmony ends national separatism and chauvinistic worldview, negates them, creates inter-ethnic environment, feelings of mental and moral trust, sincere mutual respect in expressing opinions among young people, feelings of support, assistance, help, as well as emotional, intellectual, spiritual. helps to increase communication opportunities, increase responsibility.

In this country, Uzbeks and other peoples live freely and freely, live as citizens with equal rights with the titular nation, preserve and develop their national language, culture, and traditions. becomes important.

In our country, educating young people in the spirit of tolerance and interethnic harmony is considered one of the priority directions of the state policy, and it is the task of educational institutions to study this topical issue in depth and to promote it widely. This task is to directly or indirectly study the essence, characteristics and social nature of the processes of globalization and integration within the framework of national relations, to avoid situations of social tension in polyethnic systems, issues of strengthening inter-ethnic harmony, social conflicts, phenomenological or inter-ethnic relations in everyday life, the results of which are youth subculture, migration and promotes the need for social and scientific analysis of systematic improvement of its application at the level of multicultural societies and further stabilization of inter-ethnic harmony processes. At this point, it is appropriate to quote the following comments of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev: "Developing the culture of tolerance and humanity, strengthening inter-national and inter-citizen solidarity and harmony, educating the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, is one of the most important priorities of the state policy in Uzbekistan. was determined."

In this regard, all legal bases and necessary conditions have been created to ensure inter-ethnic and inter-confessional harmony in our country. In particular, practical measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities, as well as large-scale activities conducted among young people, are aimed at strengthening the atmosphere of peace, mutual respect and harmony in our society. Forming and further strengthening the culture of tolerance is one of the priority tasks of our state policy and corresponds to the movement of the international organizations of the world community in this direction.

It is known that the Declaration on "Principles of Tolerance" was adopted at the 28th session of the UNESCO General Conference on November 16, 1995. Since then, November 16 has been widely celebrated throughout the world, including in our country, as the International Day of Tolerance. The main purpose of tolerance is to encourage mankind to maintain peace and tranquility. As stated in this declaration: "There is no peace without tolerance, and without peace there is no development and democracy."

In order to improve the effectiveness of spiritual and educational activities among young people and to widely inculcate the ideas of interethnic harmony and tolerance, a number of legal documents have been adopted in our country. In particular, in Article 19 of our General Dictionary, "human rights and freedoms are recognized and guaranteed in the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the generally recognized norms of international law and in accordance with this Constitution." Human rights and freedoms belong to everyone from birth. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, belief, social origin, and social status.

In order to ensure the stability of civil harmony, peace and harmony between representatives of different nationalities, and to strengthen the feeling of a single multi-national family in the minds of our compatriots, the Committee on Inter-National Relations and Friendship Relations with Foreign Countries operates under the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan.

In order to prevent young people in our country from committing extremist and terrorist acts under the guise of religion, and to prevent them from falling under the influence of those who have not yet understood the essence of religion and are trying to attract young people to these malicious activities, from parents, neighborhood, public organizations, mass media, especially pedagogues- coaches have responsible tasks. It is necessary to show young people from historical sources that people of different nationalities and religions lived peacefully in Uzbekistan, that our ancestors always treated representatives of other religions with respect, and worked side by side for the development of the Motherland.

It should be noted that our national characteristics are connected with universal values. Over the centuries, our people have made a great contribution to the improvement of universal, universal human values. Respect for representatives of different nationalities, coexistence with them, religious tolerance, pursuit of worldly knowledge, learning of advanced experiences and culture of other nations have been inherent in our people since time immemorial. Moreover, all the religions of the world are based on the idea of goodness, which relies on several virtues such as honesty, peace, goodness and friendship. It calls people to honesty and purity, kindness, humanity and tolerance.

In conclusion, the basis of stable maintenance of tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony is related to the citizens, first of all, the youth, being well informed about the state language, national literature, history and culture. After all, only people who have studied history, whose national values, religious faith and others can respect, and who have read fiction, will develop attention and love for other nations, and the spirit of mutual solidarity will increase in the society.

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